

Abstract**Comparison of Efficacy and Side Effects Tolerability Between Tramadol and Diclofenac in Patients with Non-Specific Low Back Pain**

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Background. High prevalence of Non-specific low back pain (NCLBP) is a significant public health concern. We compare the effectiveness and safety of tramadol retard and diclofenac SR for pain relief and functional outcome in patients with NCLBP.

Materials and Methods: This study assessed two groups of NCLBP patients on either diclofenac SR 100mg bd or tramadol retard 100mg bd. The primary outcomes measured were changes in the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) for pain and the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) for function at 3 weeks (short-term) and 12 weeks (intermediate-term).

Results: Both the diclofenac and tramadol groups showed statistically significant improvements in VAS and ODI scores from pre-intervention values at both the 3-week and 12-week periods. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in the level of improvement observed in pain relief or functional outcome. Side effects were reported by 35% of patients on diclofenac (mostly nausea, epigastric discomfort, and pain) and 37.5% of patients on tramadol (nausea, anxiety, dizziness and sleep disturbance). Only one patient (7.14%) stopped diclofenac due to adverse effects, while a greater percentage of patients (13%) stopped tramadol due to intolerable side effects. The use of muscle relaxants by over half the patients in both groups may have contributed to better pain relief.

Conclusion: Both tramadol retard and diclofenac SR are effective and comparably safe for pain relief and functional improvement in selected NCLBP patients over short and intermediate terms. The addition of muscle relaxants should be considered to enhance pain relief.

Keywords: Chronic low back pain, diclofenac, tramadol, side effect, visual analogue score, Oswestry disability index.

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